

Heteroaromatic Annulations for the Synthesis of Bridge-head Nitrogen Compounds via α -Oxoketene Dithioacetals

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The discovery of our aromatic and heteroaromatic annulations involving the reaction of allyl¹, benzyl², propargyl³ magnesium halides, lithioacetonitrile⁴, Reformatsky reagents⁵, 2-picolyllithium⁶, 5-lithiomethylisoxazoline⁷, 2-lithiomethylthiazoles and 2-lithiomethylthiazoline⁸, and the lithium enolates derived from 1,3,6-trimethyluracil⁹ and 3-pyrrolidinocrotonates¹⁰ with α -oxoketene dithioacetals **1** (Scheme 1) have been shown to be of general applications to yield the corresponding aromatic and heteroaromatic compounds with diverse structural features in high yields. The overall process was aimed at creating an aromatic (or heteroaromatic) ring systems from the easily available acyclic aliphatic precursors. The method offers for the first time an one-pot reaction process for the construction of aromatic rings from the open-chain precursors involving the combination of two three-carbon fragments of which one possessed 1,3-dielectrophilic centres and the other 1,3-dinucleophilic centres.

The α -oxoketene dithioacetals (**1**) derived from a variety of active methylene ketones and aldehydes constitute a large number of 1,3-electrophilic fragments that lend scope for liberal structural variation in the product aromatics. Similarly, a variety of allylanions as described above have been examined^{1-3,11} as useful 1,3-dinucleophilic fragments. These anions have been shown to undergo facile 1,2-addition to the α -oxoketene dithioacetals to give the corresponding carbinolacetals in nearly quantitative yields. The carbinolacetals were then subjected *in situ* with Lewis acid catalysed cyclisation to afford the corresponding benzoannulated products. Thus a large variety of benzenoids, naphthalenes, phenanthrenes, anthracenes, benzanthracene and many other condensed aromatics were synthesised by choosing appropriate allyl¹, benzyl², 1-(or 2-)naphthylmethyl¹¹ anions and α -oxoketene dithioacetals. For the synthesis of substituted benzenes this approach is novel since the literature methods follow the substitution on the preconstructed aromatic ring. Such an approach suffers some limitations due to rigid aromatic orientation. In the present method, the desired substituents could be placed either in the open-chain dielectrophilic fragment or in dinucleophilic fragment or in both, if required. Thus, we can exercise control on the substituent pattern in the product aromatics. Also a variety of 1- or 1,3-heteroatom binucleophiles can be used so that an heteroatom or atoms can be incorporated in the aromatic ring. Another important variation is the successful construction of aromatic ring over the preconstructed

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

heterocyclic product, which provides a new route for benzoheterocycles and related condensed heteroaromatics^{1,10}. Earlier we had developed an efficient method for the synthesis of alkoxy-pyrimidines and their condensed analogs by reacting **1** with guanidine in the presence of the corresponding alcohol and its sodium salt¹². Similarly, pyridones¹³ and 1,7-naphthyridines were prepared by condensing **1** with cyanoacetamide derived anions as 1,3-binucleophiles. Recently, yet another new route for substituted and annelated pyridines (quinolines, phenanthridines etc.) was reported by reacting **1** with lithioacetonitrile⁴, lithio-propionitrile⁴ and lithio-β-substituted-β-aminoacrylonitriles¹⁴. Similarly, biologically important substituted and annelated 9-diazapteridines were synthesised by cyclisation of **1** with 6-aminouracil⁹. Our efforts to further generalise the efficacy of this methodology are still being continued to encompass major areas of heterocyclic chemistry. We present in this short review only those reactions which yield bridge-head nitrogen compounds through heteroaromatic annelation via α-oxoketene dithioacetals.

oxoketene dithioacetals of general formula **1** derived from aliphatic and cyclic active methylene ketones have been liberally used to demonstrate efficacy of the method to afford the structural diversity in the products. The 1,3-binucleophilic species (**5**) are those which have one or two heteroatom situated either at 3- or 1,3-positions so that the product generally contains a bridge-head nitrogen in the condensed heterocycle. Thus the azaallyl anions (**5-8**) derived from 2-picoline (**5**), 2-methylquinoline (**6**), 2-methylthiazole (**7**) or thiazoline (**8**) and 2-aminopyrazole (**9**) were selected as representative examples for the construction of bridge-head nitrogen heterocycles.

Scheme 3

In Scheme 1 the approach for the construction of bridge-head nitrogen is depicted. The α-

2-Picolylithium (**5a**; Scheme 2) was reacted with α -oxoketene dithioacetals (**1a**) at -15° when the corresponding carbinolacetal (**10a**) was formed in quantitative yield. The intermediate (**10a**) without isolation was treated with $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ in refluxing benzene when the corresponding 4-phenyl-6-methylthioquinolizinium tetrafluoroborate (**12a**) was formed in 82% yield. Similarly, other 4-substituted-quinolizinium salts (**12b-f**) were obtained in 73–84% overall yields (Table). The cyclic dithioacetals (**1g-h**) also yielded the corresponding quinolizinium salts (**12g, h**) in 82 and 79% yields respectively. The reaction was equally facile with cinnamoyl ketene dithioacetals (**1i, j**) and dienoyl ketene dithioacetals (**1k, l**) to afford the corresponding enyl quinolizinium salts (**12i, j**)

and dienyl quinolizinium salts (**12k, l**) in 79–83% overall yields (Scheme 2)⁶.

To extend the method for the synthesis of condensed quinolizinium salts (**12m-q**), the appropriately functionalised dithioacetals (**1m-q**) derived from tetralones (**1m-o**), benzthiepenone (**1q**) and benzoxipenone (**1p**) were condensed under identical conditions with 2-picolylithium to afford excellent overall yields of **12m-q** (Scheme 2).

The methylthio-substituted quinolizinium salts (**12**) thus obtained failed to undergo desulphurisation in the presence of Raney nickel hydrogenolysis. However, the methylthio group was easily replaced by ethoxy group during hydrogenolysis in the presence of ethanol. The alternative approach for the synthesis of quinolizinium salts which are free from methylthio group was best achieved by reacting β -oxodithioacetals (**13a-e**) with **5** under the described reaction conditions to afford the corresponding sulphur-free quinolizinium salts (**14a-e**) in 70–83% overall yields (Scheme 3). The required β -oxodithioacetals (**13a-e**) were conveniently prepared in 80–95% overall yields employing our own method involving the reduction of **1** with either sodium borohydride in the presence of acetic acid¹⁵ or zinc in acetic acid¹⁶. The yields of **13** were shown to be better when the reduction of **1** was carried out with zinc in acetic acid. Thus, it is possible to convert **1** under very simple reaction condition to β -oxodithioacetals (**13**) in high yields which are useful intermediates for the synthesis of the corresponding quinolizinium tetrafluoroborates (**14**; Scheme 3).

The α -oxoketene dithioacetals (**1a-q**) were similarly condensed with 2-lithiomethylquinoline (**6**) under identical reaction conditions to afford the corresponding methylthiobenzol[*a*]quinolizinium tetrafluoroborates (**16a-q**) in 61–89% overall yields¹⁷ (Scheme 4). Here again the methylthio group could not be removed under Raney nickel disulphurisation conditions. Some sulphur-free

Scheme 4

fluoroborates (**16b**, **16i**, **16k**, **16o**) could be obtained by reacting the β -oxodithioacetals (**13**) under the described reaction conditions (Scheme 4).

Scheme 5

In continuation of this strategy we further investigated the reaction of 2-lithiomethylthiazoles (**7a** and **7b**) and 2-lithiomethylthiazoline (**8**) with α -oxoketene dithioacetals with a view to for-

mulating an efficient methodology for the synthesis of thiazole and dihydrothiazolo[3,2-*a*]pyridinium salts of general formula **19** (Scheme 5), **21** (Scheme 6) and **25** (Scheme 7)⁸.

The 2-lithiomethyl-5-methylthiazole underwent facile 1,2-addition with **1** to afford the corresponding carbinolacetal (**17**) at -78° which on treatment with $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ yielded the corresponding thiazolo[3,2-*a*]pyridinium tetrafluoroborates (**19a-i**) in 42–69% overall yields. It may be noted here that the construction of thiazolo[3,2-*a*]pyridinium ring systems have been described in the literature from a preconstructed 2-thiopyridine [azine approach¹⁸] or from the thiazole derivatives [azole approach¹⁹]. Generally most literature methods are confined to azine approach, and the azole approach starting from the preconstructed thiazole ring to build the pyridinium ring is scantily described in the literature. However, both the approaches do not offer much scope for the substituent variation in the pyridine ring. Thus, the α -oxoketene dithioacetal approach in this heteroaromatic annelation to construct thiazolopyridine ring systems through the lithio-

Scheme 6

thylthiazoles is an attractive alternative as demonstrated from the variation of the substituents in the pyridine ring.

The reaction was equally successful with the cyclic α -oxoketene dithioacetals (**20a-f**; Scheme 6) to afford the corresponding thiazolopyridinium systems (**21a-f**) with condensed aromatics on the pyridine ring. However, the reaction of **7a** with cyclohexanone derived ketene dithioacetals (**22**) failed to give the thiazolopyridinium salt after the treatment of the carbinolacetal (**23**) with $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ in refluxing benzene. Only the corresponding 1,1-bis(methylthio)methylene-2-(4-methylthiazolo)methylene cyclohexane (**24**) was obtained in 22% yield (Scheme 6). The superiority of the present method for the synthesis of 5-methylthio-6,7-dihydrothiazolo[3,2-*a*]pheanthroquinolizinium tetrafluoroborates (**21**) is apparent since such molecules could not be obtained by any of the earlier known methods. The reaction of 2-lithiomethylthiazoline (**8**) with **1a-d** and **20a** under identical reaction conditions yielded the corresponding 2,3-dihydrothiazolo[3,2-*a*]pyridinium tetrafluoroborates (**25a-e**) in 82–92% yields (Scheme 7).

Scheme 7

The examples selected for the synthesis of these bridge-head nitrogen heterocycles is only representative and hold considerable synthetic potential with further structural variations in the α -oxoketene dithioacetals.

The cycloaromatisation of α -oxoketene dithioacetals with 3-aminopyrazoles yielded the corresponding highly regioselectively substituted and condensed pyrazolo[*a*]pyrimidines²⁰ (Scheme 8).

R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴	Yield % 26	27
H	H	Me	H	82	68
H	H	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	H	93	75
H	H	2-thienyl	H	89	71
H	H	2-furyl	H	88	-
H	H	Et	Me	86	-
H	H	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅ CO	76	-
SMe	C ₆ H ₅	Me	H	80	-
SMe	C ₆ H ₅	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	H	93	-
SMe	C ₆ H ₅	Me	n-C ₄ H ₉	78	-
SMe	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	Me	81	-
H	C ₆ H ₅	Me	H	-	79
H	C ₆ H ₅	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	H	-	89

Scheme 8

When **9a** or **9b** were refluxed with α -oxoketene dithioacetals in glacial acetic acid in the presence of catalytic amount of piperidine the corresponding 7-substituted-5-methylthiopyrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidines (**26a-l**) were obtained in 68–89% yields (Scheme 8). The azolo[*a*]pyrimidines which are purine analogues, are of great chemical and pharmacological importance. The synthesis of these compounds have been described in the literature involving cycloaromatisation of aminoazoles with 3-carbon 1,3-electrophilic fragments such as β -ketoesters¹², β -diketones²², and β -ketoaldehydes²³ or their enol ethers and acetals²⁴. However, reaction of aminoazoles with these 1,3-carbonyl systems generally results in a mixture of regioisomers²⁵. Also, these methods do not offer much scope for the substituent and structural modification. Besides, the lack of regioselectivity is generally

Scheme 9

encountered apparently due to competitive reactivity of 1,3-electrophilic centres of the β-dicarbonyl compounds towards binucleophiles. The α-oxoketene dithioacetals on the other hand, despite possessing 1,3-electrophilic centres, display marked regioselectivity in their reaction towards the binucleophiles examined, and only one regioisomer has generally been obtained making our method extremely useful for the synthesis of pyrazolopyrimidines.

The reaction was found to be generally applicable with other α-oxoketene dithioacetals. Thus,

the 7-styryl (29a, b), 7,4-aryl-1,3-butadienyl (29c, d) and 7,6-aryl-1,3,5-hexatrienyl (29e, f) pyrazolopyrimidines were obtained in 74–89% overall yields on reaction of 1 with 9a–h (Scheme 9). The regiochemical assignments of these compounds were supported by the observed coupling constants of 4.5 Hz between H-5 and H-6 protons in ¹H nmr spectra of the reduced pyrimidine (30) obtained by Raney nickel hydrogenolysis.

The reaction was equally successful for the synthesis of annelated pyrazolopyrimidines (31–35; Schemes 10 and 11) using cyclic ketene dithioac-

Scheme 10

Scheme 11

tals. The methods described in this review are representative of each category of reactions, involving selected 1,3-dielectrophilic fragments in the form of α -oxoketene dithioacetals derived from wide structural variants of active methylene ketones and aldehydes and 1,3-dinucleophilic species either in the form of azaallyl anions or 2-aminopyrazoles. The choice of 1,3-dinucleophilic species is incomprehensive and there remains many structural variants unexplored. There are therefore further possibilities to explore these areas to more efficient novel product development for bridge-head heterocycles.

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